

Employee Selection at HSBC Bank: A comparison between the UK and Bangladesh

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Abstract:

The rapid growth of globalization of business has led to a rising need to “internationalize” human resource managers within the bank and organization. Many large multinational banks like HSBC now see the international management experience as a precondition for advancement to senior management positions. In the absence of effective selection method human resource and line managers continue to use a variety of imperfect methods to aid the task of predicting which applicant will be most successful in meeting the demands of the job and/ or are the best fit the work group and culture of the Bank and organization. This is the reason why effective and modern selection methods are very important for human resource department. This paper explains the picture of literature to the discussion of the selection process at HSBC Bank with an comparison between the United Kingdom and Bangladesh, and the impact of cultural variation in the selection procedure as well.

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Introduction

This research comprises of an analysis of the selection procedure of the HSBC Bank and shows how cultural difference affects the selection process in the United Kingdom and Bangladesh. The success of an organization or a multinational bank depends on its effectiveness, efficient workforce. A research in the UK by Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (2005b) established that 85% of multinational banks and companies have faced recruitment and selection difficulties and a shortage of experienced and expert HR professionals which are the most common factors. The contributors in the research also categorized the importance of branding in selection that organization stood as a “good employer”. Employers now-a- days are becoming more dynamic and creative to recruit and select new staffs. (Henkens et al.2005). In this research, the researcher have chosen the HSBC Bank because Hong Kong and Shanghai Bank Corporation (HSBC) Group was one of the world's largest banking and financial service organization began in the Asia more than 130 years ago headquartered in London. In HSBC Bank selection of effective employees is one of the most vital parts of the Human resource department. According to (Brunsson, 1989) selection is the assessment of making viewpoint which is a conscious choice between at least two substitute actions. Selection is basically dealing with the decision of that who will be fit in the particular job vacancy. And these kinds of decisions are made on the basis of valuation and selection of techniques and of the relative appropriateness of a group of prospective individuals who might fill the vacancy. On the other hand the selection procedure is sometimes strongly affected by cultural variation of diverse countries. Perkins and Shortland(2006) reported that, selection is a method which is used more or less regularly in different cultures. It means that, selection process and procedures are varied in multinational Banks and organization. For example, in the United Kingdom and the United States most of the banks and multinational company use “psychometric tests” in their recruitment and selection procedure. And in some banks and organizations in the UK the employer uses IQ tests and verbal reasoning elements. Because equality is one of the vital goals of recruitment and selection process, it is very essential to choose a selection method which has no disadvantage to any cultural group. On the other hand in some of the Asian country like Bangladesh the employers are not that much familiar about these kinds of tests. The purpose of this research is to find that how HSBC Bank selects employee and what methods or techniques they are used for selection and choosing the right candidate for the right position. More specifically, the study will focus on the cultural differences which can affect the selection process in HSBC Bank both in the United Kingdom and Bangladesh. As demonstrated in the literature review HSBC Bank uses effective selection methods and techniques which is sometimes strongly affected by cultural variations. Numerous scholars have classified the number of other factors which is successfully discussed in the research. For example, Derek Torrington, Laura Hill, Stephen Taylor, Ray French, Carol Atkinson and many more.

Methodology

Research methodology summarizes the aim of the study procedure and gives details about the process used to take out the research analysis. O’Leary (2004, pg, 85) recognized, the research method is, “The formation which is connected with a particular position of reports which will use to take out in our research.” According to Blaikie (2000) in Baker(2003,pg, 124), “Methodology is the vital opinion of substitute policies and methods.” Baker (2003) state that, research is concerned with opinions that is previously identified and the new arrangement during conceptualization and assumption building. In this research the

researcher collects data and analyze the data that is most important as well as the essential thing for doing research method. The data that is collected depends on the research question and observation and objectives which will give the exacting focus on the examination. In the major source of details and numbers of collection of the questionnaire and approach analysis are operate and in smaller source of data collection related notes, publications, journal and publications are used. In the business and decision making research is the most used thing is Questionnaire which is made for examination strategy. Though, both experimentation and case study research approaches can make use of this method. According to (Oppenheim 2000), the questionnaire is worth nothing that there are different types of definition in ordinary practice.

Literature Review

A literature review is assumed to classify the subjects that support the implementation or refusal of such a procedure. This will assist the development of the selection idea and also how selection procedures are implemented in the banking industry. Sometimes cultural variation affects the recruitment and selection process. Moreover, the literature of effective selection procedure in the banking industry with a specific situation to the HSBC Bank and the selection techniques will also be studied. The foundation of this literature covers periodicals and textbooks.

Selection and its Importance

No matter how the structures cultured, procedures and technology of a multinational bank, it is the ability and assurance of its workforce that make sure its achievement. Without the best possible arrangement of individuals at changed levels, with suitable abilities, information and motivation, specific and Bank performance will suffer. (Banfield and Kay 2008). So, it is therefore necessary for the success of the Bank to make sure that the selection is efficient and delivers the highest caliber of employees at best expenditure. Selection is one of the essential parts of Human Resource Management. Selection of employees is one of the main human resource functions in work organizations. Employee selection mentions to the procedure that employers use to take decisions regarding which persons from a group to choose for particular jobs or roles within the organization. (Pfeffer and Sutton, 2006). For an example, a study in manufacturing organizations (Patterson et al., 1997) found that, the gaining and progress of employee talents through the use of recruitment, selection, training, induction and assessment have a very encouraging impact on company productivity and profitability. So, in HSBC Bank, they have different selection procedures in different categories. The way HSBC Bank are used as the method of selection are like telephone interview, psychometric tests, ability test, online numerical and verbal test and many more. (HSBC 2011)

A role of selection in Banking Industry

Now a days in bank industry human resource management is one of the most vital issues. In most Banking organizations, the role of human resource division is not unknown by other divisions. In fact, good human resource can be one of the most valuable and respectful departments in any banking organization. In the banking industry, selection is one of the most important and essential factor that enhance the proficiency also. According to Hasnat et Al. (2009) the banking business is one of the vital and prospective industries upon which development of a country depends a lot. In Bangladesh the banking industry is very helpful for the economic development. This industry is so big which holds a lot of good talents and efficient employees. So it can be said that without effective and efficient employees the

development of any banking industry will suffer in Bangladesh. HSBC is known as the world's local bank. It also has extended to the Bangladeshi market not only increase up the banking sector also the total development of the country as well as to develop the economic condition as well. To compete with the international challenge HSBC has developed an expert and well-organized staff force. This huge employee strength is supervised totally by the HR department of HSBC Bank.

Cultural Factors (UK)

The UK, as its full name implies, is United Kingdom contains four nations: Scotland, England, Wales and Northern Ireland, each of them have their own distinguishing cultural uniqueness. However, they also share a lot of familiar principles and organization which are joined together. According to Tayeb, M.H. (1998), the British people is extremely individualistic and deeply assist their individual independence, at the same time they are very much careful about their community and employ in united actions when for an example they oppose with specific government policies. This communism is established also in the UK's strong trade union societies whose roots can be traced to the 18th and 19th century. Like for example, in the UK the employees who are working in the bank or in other company have faced the trade unionism and sometimes their selection and recruitment procedure are strongly affected by these. In an individualistic society, selection procedures are used that offer applicants with the opportunity to establish their individual capabilities and that classifies the most competent applicants (McFarlin and Sweeney, 2001). On the other hand, personal self-sufficiency is highly valued in individualistic cultures, employers more likely to select candidates on the basis of the candidate's skills, personal motivation, and self-confidence (Rousseau and Tinsley, 1997). According to Tayeb, M.H. 1998, The employee's start bargaining with the employers for better payment, good working conditions and the social system and class struggle. And on the other hand, Individualism shows also to influence the connection among employees and their bosses and their work organizations. British employees, different for example their Japanese counterparts, they never look forward to their managers to look after them and to assist them when they are facing individual difficulties. In other words, the British managers and workers have less friendly relationship and very task-oriented with one another in the office (Tayeb 1994). The British employees and American employees, both are career-oriented and they always join in new company whenever they get better prospects and signals. In Hofstead (1980) studies shows that, Britain Secord low power distance which is similar to many other nations, but people do not really care as much about fairness as they do about liberation. Both inside and outside the workplace in Britain are respectful to their superiors. So in the selection procedure of HSBC Bank UK faced the low power distance as well as the trade unionism. According to Tayeb, M. H. (2005), the class structure is returned in the diverse actions according to physical workers and low-level organization workers in Banks and companies in the United Kingdom. Managers and other white color labors usually get better benefit over physical labors in many respects such as authority, position, pay, manual working environment, eating places, and instruction for lunch and tea breaks. And on the other hand, shop floor workers and low-rank office clerks are the subjects to a tighter a work.

Selection Process in HSBC United Kingdom

Selection is the decision making activity of "the psychological assessment of appropriateness" (Townley, 1994, p.94). A selection model indicates that of finding and building of an actual Human Resource to the relationship to achieve its aims. That's why multinational bank and

organization follows a very effective selection process and methods. (CIPD 2005) staffing, preservation and revenue report found that, the selection is the method used by the organization which is varied according to the type of employees being essential. Assessment centers are more generally used while recruiting managers, professionals and graduates. In HSBC Bank, the assessment centre includes a face to face interview, a case study and a series of other training that give the chance to display the capabilities what HSBC looking for (HSBC 2010). Online testing is most common when recruiting graduates trainees. However, interview joints with application form and orientations also (Taylor 2005:200). And the name of the technique is called "classic trio" one of the most famous and broadly used technique of staff selection. In HSBC Bank in UK follows some methods which are very effective in the process of the selection procedure. They are psychometric test, interviews, evaluation methods, work samples and many more.

Psychometric testing

Psychometric testing has been used for special purpose in mainland Europe and North America, with UK talks an intermediate view. (Drenth, 1978). The tests are based on the Psychometric form (key concept 15.1) which assumes that there is a good set of psychological characteristics for the achievement at any human action.(Kline, 1993, p.219). In HSBC Bank it's used to try the test skills. They are using the online psychometric test to maintain to screen their presentation amounts, and many applicants do not meet the standard at this period. (HSBC Holdings 2011). The term psychometric test is trying to define a variety of tools and tools are calculated to degree separate change in areas such as nature, aptitude and capability. Smith and Robertson (1993: 161) defined that, psychometric tests as carefully selected, organized and normalize actions for suggesting an example of answers from an applicant, which can be used to measure one or additional emotional features by matching the results with those descriptive sample of a proper population. So in HSBC Bank psychometric tests is one of the vital part of the selection process, by using these tests HSBC evaluate the intelligence and the amount of mental skills. And also it can help them to measure the personality traits. (HSBC Holdings2011)

Interviews

An interview is a communal meeting between a candidate and a representative, or a representative of an employer and personalized the recruitment and selection process. Interviews permit an assessment and to make the applicant's personality, ability and overall suitability for the job. In HSBC Bank interview is going in a very efficient system. The interviewer asks some question about the HSBC Bank and the particular business area and the candidate should answer the question in a very effective way (HSBC private Bank 2011). On the other hand, Barclay(2001:81) advises that, selection of interviews complete a social function of advertising, discussing and influencing, they are extensively satisfactory to both managers and candidates and they are more time-efficient and less expensive than other methods such as testing or assessment centre. In HSBC Bank interviews are organized and capability-based. The employer tries to understand the employees' competence and to find out the capabilities. And they also ask some specific examples which explain capabilities (HSBC private Bank 2011). However, the interview can take in changing methods and can vary in policy, construction and motivation. The design of selection interviews can, for example variety from a single face to face conference, done in a section interview where numerous examiners interview the candidates at an only event. Selection interviews can also vary in the degree of construction accepted. On the other hand, Blackman (2002a) examined

the exercise of telephone interviews, a collective way of showing easy interviewees. The training was expected as causal if unplanned character decisions about job candidates would come from telephone interviews in judgment to face to face interviews, given the lack of vital non-verbal communication. In HSBC Bank the telephone interview is very flexible, as they are often able to offer evening and weekend time slots.(HSBC private Bank 2011).

Evaluation methods

Evaluation method is one of the most important and essential things for the selection procedure. HSBC Bank uses the evaluation method in the time of their employee selection need. (Smith, 1991, p.32) suggested that, there are some criteria as well as methods which are effective in the selection procedure. They are: - Practicality- selection process must be practiced in a given condition. For an example, cost, convenience and time available. The HSBC selection process is also very cost effective, and time obtainable. (HSBC private Bank 2011). Sensitivity- The ability of a method to differentiate one applicant from another. Reliability- It means that how to contrast more time and interpreter consistency and also the inside stability. Validity- In the validity there are some types of validity, they are, face validity, which is very important because it's essential that candidates believe that they have been fairly treated.

Work Sample

Work sampling is a method of selection of employees that provide opportunities for applicants to get knowledge or create the tasks of the job and for the employing organization to examine and review the candidates' competencies and performances (Fowler, A. 1998). In HSBC the employer uses the work sampling technique to offer the chance for the applicant to gain knowledge and make job task for the bank to judge the candidate's performances. (HSBC 2010). Work sample has shown some of the highest strength score, evaluate with other selection methods. (Smith, Gregg and Andrews, 1989, p.70). Work sampling opportunities is real where applicant really does job tasks which are performed through role play or management games. So, in HSBC bank the methodical approach to work samples can be dissuaded because it presents proposed confronts, is determined in terms of time, people and other resources.

Assessment Centre's

Assessment Centre engages assembling in one position with numerous candidates who are applying to the similar situation and put them in a selection of special test. According to CIPD (2009b), evaluation centre is employing for the collection of an amount of workers by over a third of organizations. However, the amount of applying amplify very harshly with the size of the employer (they are used by 75% of organizations employing over 5000, people, but only by 20% of those employing less than 200 staffs). Evaluation Centre's have usually been related to decision-making job, they are now frequently used for the graduate staffing purpose as well as some expert appointments, in support thought and evaluation of personality requests of an organization. Assessment Centre can also provide the candidate a practical job sample as the tasks place must personally match with those outlines in the job report and person requirement. In HSBC Bank, most of them programmers', the assessment centre includes a case study and a series of other movements that a candidate has the possibility to show the capability for what they are looking for. The event has two ways, so the candidate can decide as much as they can choose the program that is a right method. Most of the carry out which is whole will be based around the virtual scenario. So the applicant also

takes measurement in a virtual client or inside associate conference, where the evaluator will take part in a variety of client roles. (HSBC 2010)

HSBC in Bangladesh

HSBC Holdings PLC, a worldwide bank and economic services company with an idea to be the principal economic services company in Bangladesh, where the headquarters is in the United Kingdom. (HSBC, Bangladesh, 2011). In Bangladesh, the HSBC Group first starts their business in 1996 when The Shanghai and Hong Kong Corporation opened their first division. Today, the HSBC Group deals with wide-ranging variety of monetary facilities in Bangladesh with profitable investment, customer finance, expenses and cash supervision, skill services, capital, and protection and payment. With five branches, HSBC suggests a full variety of private investment and associated with economic facilities with present and moneys accounts, private loans, time payments, travelers' checks and private & external payments. HSBC has branches on Sonargaon Road (Anchor branch), Dhanmondi, Gulshan, Motijheel and Chittagong. The bank also has financial booths in Dhanmondi, Motijheel, Uttara, Gulshan and Banani. Around 300 staff is working for this bank all over Bangladesh. Now a day's HSBC group Bangladesh recommended a full variety of financial services in Bangladesh including beneficial banking, consumer banking, world-wide payments and cash management, trade services, treasury, care and clearing services. Today, the HSBC Group offers a full variety of monetary services in Bangladesh including profitable banking, consumer banking, worldwide expenditure and cash management, trade services, treasury, care and clearing services. (HSBC, Bangladesh 2011)

Cultural Variation (Bangladesh)

According to (Dipboye, 1994), culture is one of the numerous strengths that can influence whether the selection process of an organization aligns more with normal/critical or a social/natural model. The traditions of Bangladesh have a strong history more than 2500 years ago. The earth, the rivers, and the lives of the common people created a sophisticated inheritance with both commonalities with, and dissimilarities from, neighboring states. It has developed over the years, surrounding the creative variety of various common groups within Bangladesh. The cultural of Bangladesh is a combination, and more than centuries has understood the power of Islam, Hinduism, Buddhism and Jainism. The rich Bangladeshi culture joins in a manner from Dravidian, Indo-Aryan, Mongol/Mughul, Arab, Persian, Turkic and Western European culture (Bangladesh.com). The inhabitant of Bangladesh is about 98% people who are culturally Bengali and speak bangles are called Bangladeshi. In Bangladesh mainly about 86% are Muslims, but Hindus comprise sizable 13% alternative. (CIA Fact book, 2008). Hofstede's (1980) found that, Bangladesh has, two major neighbors, India and Pakistan, who has the same kind of cultural variation and the similarities. In spite of differences, the culture of Bangladesh is fairly like the Indian and Pakistani cultural which consists of the chronological and spiritual belief that is required in the middle of the people of these three countries. The description of commonalities among these countries has also been the information about the researchers during individual relations and opinion explaining. This can give details about an amount of fame essentials. Once upon a time Bangladesh was a part of Indian subcontinent and with the element with Pakistan (1947-1971). Pakistan, mainly a Muslim nation with about 90% of Muslim and Pakistan has various normal perform with Bangladeshi Muslims in a situation of their common apply. (CIA Fact book, 2008). India is a good icon of both Islam and Hinduism; it too obtained educational similarities with Bangladesh. As a result, it is realistic for this study to use as the structure of the answer of

Hofstede to watch to Pakistan and India and extrapolate from this the most likely cultural scope to be established in Bangladesh. Bangladesh is a collectivist country. In collectivist culture like Bangladesh employers are not as likely to compare and rank order individuals in the process of selection decisions (Love, Bishop, Heinisch 1994). Moreover Rousseau and Tinsley (1997) propose that employee selection in a collectivist culture like Bangladesh and other Asian countries is person-centered, focuses on the fit of the recruit with the rest of the company and is based on socially constructed methods and word of mouth recruitment. And also Traindis and Bhawuk (1997) states that, in the collectivist culture employers select employees determining whether they are loyal and trusted whereas in individualist culture employers look for task competencies. In collectivist cultures like Bangladesh employers are high power distance and outside control cultures highlight fairness or need in determining among applicants. In addition, it can be suggested that, the use of this structure to assume a learn of the most widespread HR perform used by HSBC BANK to travel around that how these cultural size make themselves obvious themselves within the branded HR frame.

Selection methods of HSBC (Bangladesh)

The plan of selection is to charge the accuracy of applicant by estimating the point to which they will be talented to bring out a task successfully. It occupies on the extent to which the individuality of applicants in the language of their competencies, knowledge, experience, learning and training people. There is some important thing for the HSBC Bangladesh selection procedure. They are,

Ability Tests

Test has been used for collection purpose for more than 50 years, but there has been an important increase in the experiment used over the previous decade as the selection procedure has turned into more difficult and accurate (CIPD, 2008c). In HSBC Bangladesh, the employer uses psychometric test, intelligence test, skill test and many more the category of test used for selection is the ability and skill tests. Intelligence test can give a sign of general psychosomatic ability, and have been used for situation of individualism that are important for job arrangement and hard to determine by other process. (Lewis 1985).

Interview

Interviewing continue to be the majority of accepted selection technique. Torrington et.al (2002:242) explains an interview as a prohibited discussion with a reason, but this wide explanation encompasses an extensive variety of observing Differentiation can comprise mutually the total of interviewers and the quantity of interview stage. In HSBC Bank, the applicants who passed in the test they will face an interview with a Human Resource Management panel may consist of individual departmental interviews, decision-making within the organization, a possible administrator and a generation or some grouping of these may interview the candidate. The candidates are mostly facing the questionnaire and talking about the previous job experience and as well as their career goals. (HSBC, Bangladesh 2011).

Reference

References are basically used to find out the extra information about the candidates earlier employers, academic tutors, colleagues and associates. Armstrong (2006) suggested that the truthful information (nature of a previous job, timetable of that job, reason of leaving the job, salary, academic accomplishment) is essential, but opinions about the atmosphere and

suitability are less dependable. So in HSBC, Bank of Bangladesh, the reference is like the investigations of the applicants who are emerge to present as workers. (HSBC Bangladesh, 2011). Almost 90% of the organization take up candidate’s references, mostly or always (CIPD 2008a), references basically used in various steps in the process. Many organizations use references only for confirmation of details of the chosen candidates after the position has been offered, whereas others will request references for shortlisted candidates prior to interview In HSBC Bank Bangladesh the reference is used like, it includes the information of the earlier company to verify the applicant work documentation, performance, approach and other performances. And it also makes contact with additional job associated and individual position and verifying the educational activities. (HSBC Bangladesh 2011).

The Selection Procedure

Figure: 1 (Sources: Contract Recruitment Agencies. (UK) 2010)

Data Findings

On the basis of literature review and discussions the researcher summarizes what information the researcher found in this research by using a questionnaire and what is the percentage of employees respond about the selection process of HSBC Bank in UK and Bangladesh.

Figure: - 2: Attitude of HR Manager of HSBC Bank in United Kingdom

In figure 4.2.1 shows that in HSBC Bank (UK) 22 percent of employees respond that the attitude of HR manager is good and same percentage of employees respond that the attitude of HR manager is very good. On the other hand 32 percent of employees respond that the attitude of HR manager is excellent. And 22 percent of employees respond the HR managers' attitude is average.

Figure: - 3: Attitude of HR Managers of HSBC Bank in Bangladesh

In figure 4.2.2 it indicates that 30 percent of employees respond that the attitude of HR manager of HSBC Bank in Bangladesh is good and on the other hand 20 percent of employees react that the attitude of HR manager is very good. And on the other hand the highest percentage of employees respond that the attitude of HR manager in Bangladesh is excellent. The percentage was about 50.

Figure: - 4: Opinion on cultural variation which affects the selection process of HSBC Bank in United Kingdom

Figure: - 4.2.3 illustrate that in United Kingdom 55 percent employees strongly agree that the cultural variation affects the selection process. On the other hand, 30 percent of employees

agree that the cultural variation affects the selection process. On the other hand, only 10 percent of employees disagree with this statement.

Figure: - 5: Opinion on cultural variation which affects the selection process of HSBC Bank in Bangladesh

Figure: - 4.2.4 indicates that about 40 percent of employees strongly agree that cultural variation strongly affects the selection procedure of HSBC Bank. On the other hand, 55 percent of employees agree with this statement that cultural variation affects the selection process.

Figure: - 6: Views on Psychometric Test in selection Procedure of HSBC Bank in United Kingdom

Figure: - 4.2.7 shows that about 22 percent of male employees strongly agree with the statement that the psychometric test should be used in the selection procedure in HSBC Bank. And on the other hand 45 percent of employees agree about the psychometric test. And in female side, 11 percent female employees disagree with the statement of using psychometric tests in HSBC Bank and 20 percent of female employees are neutral about this matter.

Figure: - 7: Views on Psychometric Test in selection Procedure of HSBC Bank in Bangladesh

In figure 4.2.8 illustrates that in HSBC Bank Bangladesh about 30 percent of male employees strongly agree that the psychometric test should be used in the selection process and only 10 percent female employees strongly agree with this statement. On the other hand, about 50 percent male employees agree with this statement about psychometric test and 10 percent of female employees agree with it.

Figure-8: Perception of E-recruiting of HSBC Bank in the United Kingdom

In this figure 4.2.11 shows that about 45 percent of male employees respond YES to the E-recruiting and selection in the selection procedure of HSBC Bank in United Kingdom. On the other hand 22 percent of males and 32 percent of female employees respond AVERAGE to the E-recruiting and selection of HSBC Bank in United Kingdom.

Figure-9: Perception of E-recruiting of HSBC Bank in Bangladesh.

In Figure: 4.2.12 denotes that 30 percent of male employee's respond YES whereas only 10 percent female employees respond YES to E-recruiting and selection. On the other hand only 10 percent of male employees respond NO to E-recruiting and selection. And about 40 percent of male employees respond AVERAGE to E-recruiting and selection, whereas only 10 percent female employees respond AVERAGE.

Analysis and Discussions

The result shows that there are various perceptions about the selection procedure in HSBC Bank in both United Kingdom and Bangladesh. The researcher found that, there are different perceptions about the attitude of HR manager of HSBC Bank in UK as well as in Bangladesh. On the basis of literature review, the researcher found that, cultural standards demonstrated in behavior during the selection procedure. In the United Kingdom the HR manager specially focuses on the candidate's body posture, the degree of eye contact, nodding and smiling. But in certain Asian countries like Bangladesh eye contact observed negatively and therefore minimized. In the UK the HR managers are very responsible for their job and very strict about the employee's selection procedure. That's why sometimes the attitude of HR manager fluctuates.

Opinion on Cultural Variation Country Cross Tabulation

On the basis of a cross tabulation sheet of cultural variation of UK and Bangladesh shows that 26.3 percent of employees strongly agree with the cultural variation of the selection procedure of HSBC Bank in UK whereas 21.1 percent of employees strongly agree with the cultural variation in Bangladesh. On the other hand 15.8 percent of employees agree with the cultural variety of the selection procedure of HSBC Bank in the UK, however 31.6 percent of employees agree with the cultural variation in Bangladesh. On the differing 5.3 percent employees totally disagree with the cultural variation and 0 percent of employees of HSBC Bank in Bangladesh are disagreeing with that. In the end it can be said that, 47.4 percent of employees from Bangladesh respond about the cultural variety of HSBC in Bangladesh whereas 52.6 percent of employees of employees respond to cultural variation of HSBC in UK. Literature shows that in an individualistic culture like the United Kingdom, draws between individuals are movable. People look out for themselves and their next family. In an individualistic society, selection procedures are used that offer applicants with the opportunity to establish their individual capabilities and that classifies the most competent applicants. (McFarlin and Sweeney 2001). And personal self-sufficiency is highly valued in individualistic cultures, employers more likely to select candidates on the basis of the candidate's skills, personal motivation, and self-confidence (Rousseau and Tinsley, 1997). In this survey research it shows that, in the HSBC Bank United Kingdom, the employees are very individualistic and self-controlled. When they select employees they use so many tests, psychometric test, IQ test and many more. They basically evaluate the employee's efficiency and effectiveness. On the other hand collectivist cultures like Bangladesh employers treating everyone in a same way and give value to everyone rather than discriminating among in groups on the basis of performance or potential (McFarlin and Sweeney, 2001) and in a collectivist culture like Bangladesh employers are not as likely to compare and rank order individuals in the process of selection decisions (Love, Bishop, Heinisch 1994). Moreover Rousseau and Tinsley (1997) propose that employee selection in a collectivist culture like Bangladesh is person-centered, focuses on the fit of the recruit with the rest of the company and is based on socially constructed methods and word of mouth recruitment. And also

Traindis and Bhawuk(1997) states that, in the collectivist culture employers select employees determining whether they are loyal and trusted whereas in individualist culture employers look for task competencies. In collectivist cultures like Bangladesh employers are high power distance and outside control cultures highlight fairness or need in determining among applicants.

Opinion of Psychometric tests on country Cross Tabulation

On the basis of the cross tabulation sheet it can be said that 10.5 percent of employees of HSBC Bank UK strongly agree with the psychometric test in the selection procedure whereas 21. And 36.8 percent of employees of HSBC Bank agree with this statement, whereas 26.3 percent of employees agree with the use of psychometric test in the selection procedure in Bangladesh. The researcher found in literature psychometric test is one of the most vital selection methods in the United Kingdom, Europe and United States. Smith and Robertson (1993: 161) defined that, psychometric tests as carefully selected, systematize and standardize activities for suggesting an illustration of answers from an applicant, which can be used to measure one or additional emotional features by matching the results with those descriptive sample of a proper population. Psychometric tests have the great reputation as the best selection interpreters of job performance across almost all types of jobs. (Schmidt and Hunter,1981). In HSBC Bank psychometric tests is one of the dynamic parts of the selection process, by using these tests HSBC estimate the intelligence and the amount of mental skills. And also it can help them to measure the personality traits. (HSBC Holdings2011). The research survey shows that in the HSBC Bank United Kingdom most of the male employees strongly agree with the psychometric test, whereas some female employees were neutral on that matter. Because female employees are not that much psychologically strong and some time feels confused about these kind of tests. But male employees in the United Kingdom are more versatile and intelligent. Psychometric test is the way to justify the candidate's ability, psychological characteristics and many more. In the literature review researcher found that, CIPD (2009) shows 44 percent of organization in the UK using general ability tests and 39 percent of organization using literacy/numeracy tests and 35 percent using personality tests. On the other hand, in Asia like Bangladesh psychometric test is not that much familiar towards the employer as well as employees. But in this research the researcher found that the employees have strongly agreed to the use of psychometric test in HSBC Bank in Bangladesh because HSBC Bank is an international banking organization. So, to work internationally it is important for the Bangladeshi employees to adopt with the international professionalism.

Opinion of attitude of HR manger on country Cross Tabulation

On the basis of the cross tabulation sheet it shows that in UK 15.8 percent of employees respond the attitude of HR manager is good, whereas in Bangladesh 10.5 percent of employees respond the attitude of HR manager is good. On the same way 10.5 percent of employees in both UK and Bangladesh respond the attitude of HR manager is very good. So in total within the attitude of the HR manage within country, it can be said that in UK 52.6 percent of employees respond the attitude of HR manager is good, whereas in Bangladesh 47.4 percent of employees respond well of attitude of the HR manager. In literature review researcher found that, most of the employees of HSBC Bank United Kingdom supported organized interview. Because Ryan et al. (1999) evaluate that interview are "adversative" to the attitude of how one should carry out an interpersonal communication or the degree to which one trust the judgment of the interviewer. And also sometimes HSBC Bank (UK) does

the telephone interview, which is the most important part of their selection procedure. Because CIPD (2009) reported that 38 percent of organizations use this method of selection in the UK. On the other hand, there is evidence that telephone interviews are the best part of the structured selection rather than alone or face to face interview (Murphy 2005). On the contrary, in Bangladesh most of the employees of HSBC Bank give the average result of using structured interview. In HSBC Bank Bangladesh, the applicants who are pass the test they will face an interview with the human resource management panel may consist of individual departmental interview, decision-making within the organization, a possible administrator and a generation or some grouping of these may interview the candidate. (HSBC, Bangladesh 2011). Now a day's E-recruiting and selection is one of the important parts of the selection procedure. According to Frankland (2000) the cost of setting up a good website is approximately equal to that associated with advertising a single high-profile job in a newspaper. In this research the researcher found that in the United Kingdom, HSBC Bank most of the employees strongly agrees with the statement of E-recruiting and selection. Because for employer the main attention of E-recruiting and selection is that it permits, jobs to be promotes reasonably to a potential viewer of millions. On the other hand, in Bangladesh E-recruiting and selection is not that much familiar and popular to the employer and the employees. That's why the employees of HSBC Bank Bangladesh respond average response of E-recruiting and selection.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This chapter concludes of this study and offers some recommendations based on the key issues presented in the preceding five chapters of the study. This chapter also highlights the contributions of the study, the limitations and offers some future research directions. With the vision gained from this research some useful recommendations are made by which we can improve the selection procedure of HSBC Bank. The main aim of this research was to compare and examine the practical knowledge and the theoretical knowledge of the selection procedure of HSBC Bank in both United Kingdom and Bangladesh. And the purpose was to get knowledge about how cultural variation affects the recruitment and selection process of HSBC Bank in UK and Bangladesh. Based upon the results of the study it can be concluded that there are various differences between selection procedure of HSBC Bank in UK and Bangladesh. For example culture is one factor which strongly affects the recruitment and selection process. According to (Dipboye, 1994), culture is one of the numerous strengths that can influence whether the selection process of an organization aligns more with normal/critical or a social/natural model. In this research the researcher evaluates cultural the factors for selection practices. On the basis of this evaluation, it is advised that the cross-national differences in the faithfulness to normal/analytical and social attitudes to selection imitate the differences in these cultural dimensions. On the other hand, there are some vital issues which are explained in this research also. There are different methods of the selection procedure of HSBC Bank in both UK and Bangladesh. For an example, in UK, survey result shows that most of the employees agreed with psychometric test, whereas in Bangladesh there was an average response. Because research shows that in the UK and USA nationals use psychometric test more than the other nations in the world (Perkins and Shortland (2006). On the contrary, in Bangladesh the employers are not that much familiar about these kind of tests. These kinds of selection differences show the cultural variation in the United Kingdom and Bangladesh. And also it is necessary to explain that, cultural customs and norms also affect the attitude of the employers. In HSBC Bank in both United Kingdom and Bangladesh the attitude of HR managers fluctuates upon the basis of cultural differences. And also it is

noticeably found in my research about the difference of Interviews of HSBC Bank in UK and Bangladesh. In HSBC Bank Bangladesh the employers are not that much familiar about the telephoning interview, whereas in the UK most of the multinational organization uses this approach in their selection method. And also now day's e-recruiting and selection become more familiar in the United Kingdom, USA and other European countries. And in HSBC Bank (UK) most of the employees strongly agree with the statement, whereas in HSBC Bank Bangladesh this kind of method is not that much used in their company. So based on the results of this study it can be concluded that, cultural variation strongly affects the recruitment and selection procedure of HSBC Bank in UK and Bangladesh.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and discussions of this research it would be recommended that the selection procedure of HSBC Bank in both UK and Bangladesh has more positive and negative clarifications. Survey results show that in HSBC Bank in both UK and Bangladesh there are lots of differences in selection procedure. It would be recommended that HSBC Bank Bangladesh should introduce a new selection procedure which will help them to find out an actual candidate. For example, they should use Psychometric tests, IQ test, and Ability tests because of these methods, they can easily justify the candidates' efficiency and effectiveness. On the other hand structured interview/telephone interview/capability based interview are very important for selecting a good candidate. In HSBC Bank Bangladesh they are not that much familiar with this things whereas in HSBC Bank (UK) uses the telephone interview which is the most important part of their selection procedure so it would be recommended that, they should use the structured interview/telephone interview/capability based interview in their selection procedure which will help them to find out an effective candidate. In HSBC Bank, Bangladesh, the attitude of HR manager should be changed because in the time of interview the HR manager can't evaluate the candidate's body posture, degree of eye contact, nodding and smiling. These characteristics strongly focus on the candidate's personality and attitude. So the final recommendation is HSBC Bank Bangladesh should use the different types of test in their selection procedure which will help to find out the best candidates.

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Appendix

Opinion on Cultural Variation Country Cross tabulation

			Country		Total
			U.K.	Bangladesh	
Opinion on Cultural Variation	Strongly Agree	Count	5	4	9
		Expected Count	4.3	4.7	9.0
		% within Opinion on Cultural Variation	55.6%	44.4%	100.0%
		% within Country	55.6%	40.0%	47.4%
		% of Total	26.3%	21.1%	47.4%
		Residual	.7	-.7	
	Agree	Count	3	6	9
		Expected Count	4.3	4.7	9.0
		% within Opinion on Cultural Variation	33.3%	66.7%	100.0%
		% within Country	33.3%	60.0%	47.4%
		% of Total	15.8%	31.6%	47.4%
		Residual	-1.3	1.3	
	Disagree	Count	1	0	1
		Expected Count	.5	.5	1.0
		% within Opinion on Cultural Variation	100.0%	.0%	100.0%
		% within Country	11.1%	.0%	5.3%
		% of Total	5.3%	.0%	5.3%
		Residual	.5	-.5	
Total	Count	9	10	19	

Expected Count	9.0	10.0	19.0
% within Opinion on Cultural Variation	47.4%	52.6%	100.0%
% within Country	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
% of Total	47.4%	52.6%	100.0%

Group Statistics

Country	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Opinion on Cultural Variation U.K.	9	2.00	1.225	.408
Bangladesh	10	2.20	1.033	.327

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Opinion on Cultural Variation	Equal variances assumed	1.445	.246	-.386	17	.704	-.200	.518	-1.293	.893
	Equal variances not assumed			-.383	15.774	.707	-.200	.523	-1.310	.910

Psychometric Test Country Cross tabulation

			Country		Total
			U.K.	Bangladesh	
Psychometric Test	Strongly agree	Count	2	4	6
		Expected Count	3.2	2.8	6.0
		% within Psychometric Test	33.3%	66.7%	100.0%
		% within Country	20.0%	44.4%	31.6%
		% of Total	10.5%	21.1%	31.6%
		Residual	-1.2	1.2	
		Std. Residual	-.7	.7	
	agree	Count	7	5	12
		Expected Count	6.3	5.7	12.0
		% within Psychometric Test	58.3%	41.7%	100.0%
		% within Country	70.0%	55.6%	63.2%
		% of Total	36.8%	26.3%	63.2%
		Residual	.7	-.7	
		Std. Residual	.3	-.3	
	disagree	Count	1	0	1
		Expected Count	.5	.5	1.0
		% within Psychometric Test	100.0%	.0%	100.0%
		% within Country	10.0%	.0%	5.3%
		% of Total	5.3%	.0%	5.3%
		Residual	.5	-.5	
		Std. Residual	.7	-.7	
Total	Count	10	9	19	
	Expected Count	10.0	9.0	19.0	
	% within Psychometric Test	52.6%	47.4%	100.0%	
	% within Country	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% of Total	52.6%	47.4%	100.0%	

Group Statistics

country	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
psychometric test U.K.	9	3.11	1.453	.484
Bangladesh	10	2.20	1.033	.327

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
psychometric test	Equal variances assumed	.063	.805	1.589	17	.131	.911	.574	-.299	2.121
	Equal variances not assumed			1.560	14.301	.141	.911	.584	-.339	2.162

Attitude of the HR Manager Country Cross tabulation

			Country		Total
			U.K.	Bangladesh	
Attitude of the HR Manager	Good	Count	3	2	5
		Expected Count	2.6	2.4	5.0
		% within Attitude of the HR Manager	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

	% within Country	30.0%	22.2%	26.3%
	% of Total	15.8%	10.5%	26.3%
Very Good	Count	2	2	4
	Expected Count	2.1	1.9	4.0
	% within Attitude of the HR Manager	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%
	% within Country	20.0%	22.2%	21.1%
	% of Total	10.5%	10.5%	21.1%
Excellent	Count	3	5	8
	Expected Count	4.2	3.8	8.0
	% within Attitude of the HR Manager	37.5%	62.5%	100.0%
	% within Country	30.0%	55.6%	42.1%
	% of Total	15.8%	26.3%	42.1%
Average	Count	2	0	2
	Expected Count	1.1	.9	2.0
	% within Attitude of the HR Manager	100.0%	.0%	100.0%
	% within Country	20.0%	.0%	10.5%
	% of Total	10.5%	.0%	10.5%
Total	Count	10	9	19
	Expected Count	10.0	9.0	19.0
	% within Attitude of the HR Manager	52.6%	47.4%	100.0%
	% within Country	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	52.6%	47.4%	100.0%

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